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UNDERSTANDING THE IMPACT OF IDENTITY POLITICS IN THE MAKING AND IMPLEMENTATION OF NIGERIA'S FOREIGN POLICY IN THE FOURTH REPUBLIC.

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Abstract: This article explores the domestic forms of identity politics that shape and influence foreign policy making and implementation in Nigeria's Fourth Republic. The authors argue that though the external environment matters in foreign policy making and implementation, the experience of Nigeria's Fourth Republic demonstrates that a combination of both religion and ethnicity has somewhat impacted and cannot be undermined. The paper utilized domestic-level theories such as Linkage and pluralism to analyze primary and secondary sourced data. The primary data are mainly interviews conducted in Abuja and Jos with interviews that are adjudged to be knowledgeable in the subject under consideration. The secondary data includes peer-reviewed journal articles, books, and newspapers/magazines.

Keywords: Identity Politics, Religion, Ethnicity, Foreign Policy.

Introduction

In the practice and study of international relations, it is generally accepted that both domestic and external factors can influence the behavior of state actors. At the external level, the foreign policy of states has been influenced by international institutions, international standards, power dynamics, and global order.¹ At the domestic level, the most visible influences include the form of government itself and the idiosyncrasies of leaders that determine or influence foreign policy outcomes.² Be that as it may, religion and value systems, ideology, identity, and non-state actors are increasingly gaining momentum as key influencers of the foreign policy of states.³ While the above influences are acknowledged, the articulation, coordination, and implementation of a country's foreign policy is essentially reserved for the government and leadership of the state under which the foreign policy is meant to be served.

¹ Warner, Jason, and Timothy M. Shaw, eds. *African foreign policies in international institutions*. Springer, 2018.

² Holsti, Ole Rudolf. *Public opinion and American foreign policy*. University of Michigan Press, 2009.

³ Isike, Christopher, Samuel Oyewole, and Aloysius-Michaels Okolie. "The ethno-regional and religious drivers of Nigeria's foreign policy." *Revista Brasileira de Política Internacional* 67, no. 2 (2024): e019.

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The experience in Nigeria suggests that its foreign policy objectives have been almost consistent to a degree, but the execution of the cardinal principles has almost always oscillated, reflecting the psychological make-up of the leadership under which the issues emanated. Following from the above, it is safe to assert that the making and implementation of Nigeria's foreign policy have been largely influenced by a combination of domestic factors comprising ethnic interest, orientation, and ideological and psychological make-up of the leadership.⁴

From the earliest years of Nigeria's political independence, the conduct of its foreign relations has largely been influenced by a constellation of internal factors comprising colonial exploitation of identity politics that laid the foundation for ethnic strife and religious intolerance. At the very base of these various social disorders orchestrated by the colonial regime was a dislocated economic system that was structured to serve foreign interest and retain an essential duty of producing primary commodities devoid of industrialization. Other forms of social ill that have continued to inhibit the effective coordination and implementation of Nigeria's foreign relations include disdain for public opinion and interest, stubborn intolerance and ethnocentrism, manipulation of religion for political gains.⁵ The aforementioned issues continue to grow both in scale and in form and inhibiting the realization of Nigeria's grand objective of organizing the domestic front for the effective realization of its foreign policy.⁶

In spite of the clear manifestation of these domestic contradictions (religion, ethnicity and regional politics) that have had a far-reaching impact on the making and execution of Nigeria's foreign policy, not much has been done in researching the subject matter. Bearing in mind this noticeable research gap, this paper attempts to analyze the relevance the connection between religion and ethno-regional politics as crucial factors that have been determining or influencing Nigeria's foreign relations. In order words, what is known and vastly published relates to how ethno-regional politics and religion have undermined national integration efforts. However, this paper posits that these domestic forces of ethno-regional politics and religion have often extended their wings of influence beyond national politics to Nigeria's external relations. The article relies not only on secondary sources but also incorporates primary data generated through key informant interviews to analyze the crucial role of these domestic factors as they influence outcomes in Nigeria's foreign relations using three (3) specific theories of international relations, including but not limited to linkage, identity, and critical approach. The researcher hopes that the analyzed data will help to integrate domestic factors of religion and ethno-regional politics in the understanding of Nigeria's external relations in the Fourth Republic. By extension, the article will help to shed more light on the drivers of foreign policy in states that share similarities of factors such as history and pluralism in developing societies.

⁴ Olusanya, Gabriel Olakunle, and Rafiu A. Akindede. "The structure and processes of foreign policy making and implementation in Nigeria, 1960-1990." (*No Title*) (1990).

⁵ Osaghae, Eghosa E., Augustine Ovuoronye Ikelegbe, Omobolaji O. Olarinmoye, and Stephen I. Okhomina. "Youth Militias, Self Determination, and Resource Control Struggles in the Niger-delta Region of Nigeria." (2011).

⁶ Campbell, John. "Religion and security in Nigeria." In *The Routledge Handbook of religion and security*, pp. 215-225. Routledge, 2012.

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Theories of International Relations and the domestic factors of Religion and Ethnicity

Generally, the subject of foreign policy refers to the mechanisms through which states relate to other states and non-state actors beyond their immediate borders.⁷ Thus, foreign policy can be viewed as the sum total of a state's aggregated, composed, and coherently executed moves of a state aimed at advancing its national interest within the international system. For the benefit of this article, foreign policy is used here to refer to the sum total of a state action and inaction in the course of relating with other states and non-state actors in the international system. It is within this angle that many theories have been advanced to enable readers and researchers to make meaning of foreign policy and rationalize the cause of actions and inactions of states and other entities within the broader international system. Consequently, international relations provides researchers with many theories that help to depend the understanding of the connection between these domestic factors of religion and ethno-regional politics and Nigeria's foreign policy, especially in the Fourth Republic.

To start with, the realist sees foreign policy as the aggregation of logical choices made by the state that seeks its preservation while maintaining a competitive advantage for power within the broader anarchical international system.⁸ On the other hand, rational-choice thinkers design foreign policy as the set of important decisions made by those in the corridors of power with the grand objective of maximizing gains while reducing costs.⁹ Following from the above, both realists and rational-choice theorists of international relations negate the domestic component in fashioning and executing the foreign policy choices of a given state. In a similar manner, the positions of the theories above suggest that the state and its leadership are perceived as acting or functioning on its own, and whose decisions are not impacted by such activities or issues below the national level. In other words, both rational-choice and realist thinking perceived the sub-national factors of religion, ethnic groups, and ethno-regional politics as irrational in their attempts to formulate, design, and execute foreign policy. From the foregoing, it is important to note that these Western-focused theories negate the nature of post-colonial African states that are inherently subjected to the crisis of legitimacy.

In response, international relations experts have made significant attempts to build critical theories. In no particular order, Marxism views the state simply as a board of the most significant bourgeoisie. The state is equally perceived as a tool designed for the exploitation of the proletariat class and foreign policy as merely an extension of capitalist interests.¹⁰ Closely related to Marxism is the dependency theory that critiques the creation of Western-style states in non-Western societies and the broader exploitation of the periphery states through the imposition of foreign policy mechanisms that perpetuate continuous domination of the world system by the core states.¹¹ In the middle of these struggles, Afrocentrism has risen to challenge the continuous imposition of Western-style

⁷ Milner, Helen V., and Dustin Tingley. "Sailing the water's edge: The domestic politics of American foreign policy." (2015): 1-352.

⁸ Starr, Harvey. "Introduction: the future study of international relations, two-level games, and internal-external linkages." In *Approaches, levels, and methods of analysis in international politics: Crossing boundaries*, pp. 1-9. New York: Palgrave Macmillan US, 2006.

⁹ Brown, Andrew D. "Identities and identity work in organizations." *International journal of management reviews* 17, no. 1 (2015): 20-40.

¹⁰ Barrow, Clyde W. *Critical theories of the state: Marxist, neomarxist, postmarxist*. Univ of Wisconsin Press, 1993.

¹¹ Nkrumah, Kwame. *Neo-colonialism*. Vol. 265. Cheltenham: Nelson, 1965.

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states in Africa and has called for reform of foreign policy practice towards the complete unification of the black world.¹²

The combination of Marxism, dependency, and Afrocentrism theories has helped to provide critical perspectives to the questions of post-colonial African states and the nature and configuration of their foreign policy. In spite of that, these interpretations have not adequately address the significance of the connection between religion and ethno-regional politics in Nigeria and the Fourth Republic in particular. For instance, the whole gamut of Marxism merely downsize identity to a class issue. It also represented religion not as a force in foreign policy matters but merely as an oppressive tool. Similarly, dependency theory excessively narrowed their views toward the international design of global exploitation of colonized societies through deliberate integration of these societies into the global capitalist network while neglecting the important role of identity politics in foreign policy making and implementation. On its part, Afrocentrism focused on forging regional identity through the parameters of collective bargaining for the African region while overlooking the essential diversity of the African states at subnational, national, and international levels. But it is important to note that attempts have been made to address some of the noticeable gaps. For instance, the introduction of the African realism perspective, though largely unpopular in other climes, which introduced the patrimonial character of African states with diverse stakeholders, has, in a way, helped to expose readers and researchers to the peculiar composition of Africa's international relations.¹³

Besides African realism theory, pluralism theory has equally attempted to offer a holistic approach to the study of foreign policy with a nuanced integration of the composite domestic stakes and interests. The pluralist view significantly integrated both stakeholders within the state and out of it.¹⁴ Within the pluralists, the bureaucratic stance centralized the role of the state over other entities.¹⁵ But the liberal pluralists have since acknowledged the relevance of non-state actors in foreign policy decision making and implementation.¹⁶ Further to this, identity theory has added greater impetus to local interest groups such as the case of racial platforms in the United States of America and other core Western liberal states. Also, references has been made to this special groups in developing societies – ethno-religious organizations that seek to advance this sort of primordial interest in the making and execution of foreign policy.¹⁷ The underlying consideration of these theories relates with their flexibility in acknowledging the fact that foreign policy can be better when local and pressing domestic interests are harvested from both state and non-state quarters. It is this domestic angle that is the concern of this paper.

¹² Falola, Toyin, and Kwame Essien, eds. *Pan-Africanism, and the politics of African citizenship and identity*. New York: Routledge, 2014.

¹³ Mazrui, Ali A. "Francophone nations and English-speaking states: imperial ethnicity and African political formations." In *State Versus Ethnic Claims*, pp. 25-43. Routledge, 2019.

¹⁴ Milner, Helen V., and Dustin Tingley. "Sailing the water's edge: The domestic politics of American foreign policy." (2015): 1-352.

¹⁵ Halperin, Morton H., and Priscilla Clapp. *Bureaucratic politics and foreign policy*. Bloomsbury Publishing USA, 2007.

¹⁶ Brighi, Elisabetta. *Foreign policy, domestic politics and international relations: the case of Italy*. Routledge, 2013.

¹⁷ Aleyomi, Michael B. "Religion and Global Politics: Soft Power in Nigeria and Beyond: edited by Olusola Ogunnubi and Sheriff Folarin, Lanham, Maryland, Lexington Books, 2022, ix+ 295 pp." (2023): 751-752.

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Some scholars have gone further to internationalized identity politics, arguing that identity can originate from the local but has the tendency for both cooperation and conflict at the international level.¹⁸

While pluralism viewpoint has been widely acknowledged for its effort in integrating local and domestic concerns in international relations in general and foreign policy in particular, it has equally come under criticism for its excessive reliance on identity in foreign affairs related matters. Notwithstanding, it enable researchers and policymakers to appreciate the value of identity in the period after the Cold War and to appreciate how it has influenced outcomes around the world.

One theory that incorporates the two basic levels through which international relations is conducted relates to the linkage theory. At the very general level, it maintains the two complementary layers (internal and external environments) through which international relations in general, and foreign policy in particular can be conducted.¹⁹ Among other things, it seeks to connect domestic happenings (internal) with the global (external) ones and try to probe the extent of their influences. It can be argued that linkage theory is limited in that it is silent on the specific issues to focus on when making an assessment of the two levels of international relations, applying it along with theories can help to make inform decision.

Following from the above, the understanding of the interplay between domestic factors of religion and ethno-regional politics and its influence on foreign policy making and execution can best be done through a constellation synthesis of identity, pluralism, and linkage theories. More so, the incorporation of realism and rational-choice theories can help to complement the inadequacy of the identity, pluralism, and linkage theories in an attempt to understand the influence of the domestic or internal forces of religion and ethno-regional politics in foreign policy making and implementation, and the entire spectrum of international relations. It is in light of this that this paper will first look at Nigeria's religious and ethno-regional credentials.

Nigeria's Religious and Ethno-regional Credential

Nigeria is arguably one of the most populous states in Africa.²⁰ In relation to its numerical strength, Nigeria has been adjudged by sociologists to be one of the most heterogeneous states in Africa. It is blessed with numerous natural resources.²¹ As a heterogeneous state, it prides itself on hosting both cultural and religious diversity. In light of Nigeria's plural composition, it has been argued that its exact number of ethnic groups is largely unknown.²² However, some credible ethnographic studies suggest that it is possibly hosting around 250 to 500 ethnic groups. These groups are spread all over the country. While the Northern part of the country is home to the Hausa, Fulani, and Kanuri groups, the Middle Belt is home to the diverse minority ethnic groups, including the Tiv, Taroh, Berom, Igala, Epira, and numerous others.²³ The Southern part is home to Yoruba, Igbos, Ijaw, Ishekiri, and so many others. The numerical composition of the various ethnic groups are not entirely the same. As a result, the major ethnic groups, including the Hausa, Fulani, Yoruba, and Igbos, are naturally conferred with

¹⁸ It is this form of thinking that led Huntington to propound the theory of clashes of civilization

¹⁹ Mintz, Alex, and Karl DeRouen Jr. *Understanding foreign policy decision making*. Cambridge University Press, 2010.

²⁰ Over 200 million people as projected by the National Population Commission (NPC).

²¹ Stiglitz, Joseph E. "Making Natural Resources into a Blessing rather than a Curse." *Covering Oil: A Reporter's Guide to Energy and Development* (2005): 13-19.

²² Osaghae, Eghosa E., and Rotimi T. Suberu. "A history of identities, violence, and stability in Nigeria." *Centre for Research on Inequality Human Security and Ethnicity, University of Oxford* 6 (2005): 1-27.

²³ Ukiwo, Ukoha. "The study of ethnicity in Nigeria." *Oxford Development Studies* 33, no. 1 (2005): 7-23.

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the numerical advantage to influence in far greater measure the direction of national politics. Besides, Nigeria is widely regarded as one of the most religious societies in the world. It is on record as having some of the most influential religious figures in the world. Basically, it has three major religions, including Christianity, Islam, and the African religions.

Before the Nigerian area was subjected to colonial rule, these various ethnic groups practiced different political and economic systems with adamant autonomy. One important characteristic of this era was the fact that the people who were living under these different political state systems witnessed periods of cooperation and conflicts. Yet there were periods that both cooperation and conflict paved the way for competition.²⁴ When active colonization began in 1900, and the Northern and Southern Protectorates were amalgamated, the modern state was born, paving the way for the eras of colonial administration under different colonial leadership.²⁵ Considering the diverse nature of the Nigerian state, the colonial authority under Sir Arthur Richards had introduced regionalism under the Richards Constitution of 1946. The Richards Constitution had officially designated the Nigerian state as a diverse and plural society and its new constitution recognized the three major ethnic groups in the new regional government. While the move merely recognized the reality of the Nigerian state, it produced a system that created deep division amongst the various groups. Instead of forging a sense of nationalism, the regional system fertilized new sense of ethnic nationalism and ethno-regional politics.

As noted by Isike, the process leading to the establishment of the state in Africa appears more like an imposition.²⁶ The attendant implication is that the state was designed to serve the interests of those who imposed it on the African people. Consequently, the state was, without doubt, a social contract that binds the people and their leaders. This factor, more than any other, has led to the failure of nation-building in the post-colonial era. This absence of a strong and compelling social contract produced a “primordial and prebendal”²⁷ posture for the newly imposed states. In the post-colonial order, stakeholder interactions were driven by the need to fulfill ethnic and religious interests, with little regard for the public interest. The various manifestations in the first conflicts, even before the civil war, have been explained through these lenses.

The Impact of Religion and Ethno-regional Politics on the Making and Implementation of Nigeria's Foreign Policy in the Fourth Republic

After many years under military rule, Nigeria officially returned to democratic rule on the 29th of May, 1999. As a result of the change of guards, Nigeria's military decrees were replaced by a secular constitution. Right from the “earliest days of Nigeria's independence to the Fourth Republic, Nigeria has identified as a secular state. This means that the state did not align or adopt any particular religion or ethnicity, allowing its citizens the freedom to choose any faith and identify with any ethnicity.”²⁸ What we have witnessed so far is that states often do not consult their citizens on matters of foreign policy and implementation, and this lack of consultation by states has

²⁴ Bonta, Bruce D. "Cooperation and competition in peaceful societies." *Psychological bulletin* 121, no. 2 (1997): 299.

²⁵ Falola, Toyin, and Matthew M. Heaton. "Colonial Rule." (2018).

²⁶ Isike, Christopher, Samuel Oyewole, and Aloysius-Michaels Okolie. "The ethno-regional and religious drivers of Nigeria's foreign policy." *Revista Brasileira de Política Internacional* 67, no. 2 (2024): e019.

²⁷ Fakanbi, Kehinde. "Prebendal Politics and Good Governance in Nigeria's Fourth Republic: A Review." *Public Policy and Administration Research* (2018).

²⁸ Nnamdi, Oko. Interview with Ponsah Saleh, Abuja, 14th April, 2026.

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always resulted in national chaos. It is important to note that the issues that led to serious problems for the state relate to religion and ethnic matters. The following section identifies issues of religion and ethno-regional politics that drive the making and implementation of Nigeria's foreign policy from the period of the return to civilian rule.

Religion

Religion continues to hold significant influence in today's world, impacting individuals' values, actions, choices, and worldviews across all continents. Its pervasive presence is undeniable, shaping the way people perceive and interact with the world around them. It is a significant source of basic value orientation for individuals and groups of people in developed and developing countries, and this can have social and political connotations. This is particularly evident in Nigeria, where religion permeates virtually all facets of Nigerian society, from birth to death. Though, interestingly, Nigeria's Constitution defines the country as a secular state as the country did not adopt a state religion, most Nigerians identify with at least one of the three major religions (Christianity, Islam and Traditional) predominant in the country.

During the administration of President Goodluck Jonathan, a Christian from the Niger/Delta region of Nigeria, Nigeria decided to abstain from an important resolution of the United Nations Security Council that seek to end Israel's occupation of Palestine in 2017.²⁹ The Northern elites interpreted Jonathan's moves as a diplomatic support to the Israelis. Some specifically felt the abstention was a way of support to the Israeli Mission in Palestine:

"Jonathan was reluctant to condemn the killings of children, women and unarmed civilians by the brutal forces of Israel. It was so glaring that Jonathan did not want to oppose an Israeli mission in Palestine because the Americans would not be happy with him. Those of us in the North knew about it. Some religious scholars even called him out over such deafening silence in the midst of provocation against humanity."³⁰

At a general level, the majority of people in the Southern part of the country usually give their moral support against Palestine whenever the tension between Israel and Palestine resumes. Nowhere has this view been expressed more than in the opinion of one interviewee:

"We in the South would always support Israel against Palestine. The reason is that the Northerners have not hidden their intention to offer Palestine their own support. At any time, Israel is our own. We feel safe whenever Israel defends itself against terrorists. Our neighbours in the North have done the same for Palestine. Why can't we do the same?"³¹

However, in 2016, the Nigerian President Muhammadu Buhari, a Muslim from the North, declared support for a two-state solution to the Israel-Palestine conflict, contrary to the position of the United States and Britain. Most importantly, Buhari's administration deepened bilateral and multilateral ties with the Islamic states. Furthermore, Nigeria, identified with the Saudi Arabia-led military coalition against terrorism, also supported Afghanistan with the sum of \$1 million, even when the Islamist Boko Haram also threatened the country.³²

²⁹ De Beaumont, Gustave. *Ireland: Social, Political, and Religious*. Harvard University Press, 2009.

³⁰ Adamu, Balarabe. Interview with Ponsah Saleh, Kaduna, 15th February, 2026.

³¹ Tamuno, John. Interview with Ponsah Saleh, Abuja, 10th January, 2026.

³² Isike, Christopher, Samuel Oyewole, and Aloysius-Michaels Okolie. "The ethno-regional and religious drivers of Nigeria's foreign policy." *Revista Brasileira de Política Internacional* 67, no. 2 (2024): e019.

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Again, in October 2023, Nigeria, under President Tinubu, a Muslim from the South, was part of the 120 countries that voted in favour of a draft resolution for the immediate ceasefire in the Israel-Hamas war at the United Nations General Assembly, as against the US, Israel, and 12 others that voted against it. These show the inconsistency in Nigeria's external position, interpretation of foreign policy objectives, and definition of national interest, despite the consistency in letter. Read the response of an interviewee:

"It is difficult to understand how the Buhari administration came to befriend the terrorist Taliban government in Afghanistan to the point of donating funds to them. "CHRICED categorically denounces this indiscriminate use of the nation's funds, especially in these trying times. Aside from making little or no economic sense, such a gift should not come from a government that claims to be fighting terrorism within its borders."³³

Nigeria can boost its soft power and the promotion of a positive image for the country through two important tools: Faith-Based Organizations and Religious Tourism. These FBOs provide some social services, including education and health care, are usually involved in community development initiatives, and they have local and international relevance. Their activities and programmes can help showcase Nigeria's commitment to social welfare and improve its image. For instance, the RCCG has carved out a niche for itself in terms of its public function, social significance, and local-global influence in Africa and beyond, which is best conveyed by its demographic distribution rather than just its vertical and horizontal expansion.³⁴ The RCCG challenges obstacles to development and civic involvement in addition to making significant contributions to social capital that bridge, bond, and link. Its houses of worship are not just places of worship; they are also sites of social interaction where discussions about politics, business, music, home cultures, education, and other forms of interactions take place. These places frequently cross socio-ethnic, racial, class, gender, and generational lines. People from various backgrounds come into contact with one another, engage in activities together, and often depend on one another. These make it easier for people to connect and develop bridges between local and global networking trends, new types of associations, and shared community efforts.

Ethnicity/Personality Traits of the Leadership

Apart from religion, ethnicity, which also overlaps with religion and regional politics in Nigeria, is another important variable in the country's foreign policy. The mutual mistrust among the majority ethnic groups (Yoruba, Igbo, and Hausa-Fulani) in the country, and between them and the minority groups within their respective regions, flows from national politics into foreign policy.³⁵ A few examples will suffice. Despite the official claims that foreigners from Niger are deeply involved in armed banditry, terrorism, and insurgency in the country, President Buhari publicly identified the immigrants as his kinsmen, failed to contain illegal migration across the North, but encouraged it with the construction of a transborder train, and emboldened them with the nationalization of many Fulani.³⁶ Meanwhile, the same president closed many border posts in the South, as a measure to counter

³³ Ali, Dangana Yelwa. Interview with Ponsah Saleh, Abuja, 25th March, 2026.

³⁴ Adogame, Afe. "African Christianities and the politics of development from below." *HTS: Theological Studies* 72, no. 4 (2016): 1-11.

³⁵ Onah, Emmanuel Ikechi. "Nigeria: A country profile." *Journal of International Studies* 10 (2014): 151-162.

³⁶ Ojo, J. S., F. Aina, and S. Oyewole, (Eds.). *Armed banditry in Nigeria: evolution, dynamics and trajectories*. Cham: Palgrave Macmillan, 2024

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smuggling, despite the appeal from business communities and governments of the affected federating states and neighboring countries.

Another example that speaks to the differential treatment Nigerian citizens abroad get from their government is the case of Nigerians from the South who were convicted of drug peddling and sentenced to death in Indonesia. Abike Dabiri-Erewa, Chairman of Nigerians in Diaspora Commission (NIDCOM), profiled the prisoners by stating that out of the 21 Nigerian drug peddlers on death row in Indonesian prison, 20 of them were from Anambra state, while the remaining one was from Edo state, going to the extent of mentioning their names to buttress her point.³⁷ This was widely condemned by stakeholders from the South who interpreted it as ethnic profiling of Igbo people in Nigeria as criminals abroad. Now, those affected are first Nigerians and should be regarded as such instead of linking them to their ethnic groupings. Months later, another group of Nigerians, from different ethnic extraction, including Yorubas like Abike Dabiri-Erewa, were convicted and sentenced to death also for drug dealing in Thailand, and in their case, she refrained from listing their names or states of origin as she had done previously with the Igbos. While this is interpreted as ethnocentric motivated double standard by many, some considered it as a cautious move by Abike after the blowback of her earlier insensitivity on such matter.³⁸

The recent (2023) aborted foreign policy position of Nigeria-led ECOWAS bloc on the use of military means to restore civil rule to Niger Republic under the chairmanship of President Bola Ahmed Tinubu has also received ethnocentric interpretation and reactions. Beside the general shortage of public support and the effort of the legislature to caution the President, the hardline foreign policy position of Nigeria came under the attacks of many Northern elites, who consider such as an invasion on their brothers and sisters in the Niger Republic.

Notably, the 26.3 million population of Niger Republic are made up of Hausa (53.1%), Fulani (6.5%) and Kanuri (5.9%), which double as the dominant ethnic groups in Northern Nigeria. As expected by the pluralist and identity perspectives, interest groups from this ethno-regional background played major role in soften the hardline foreign policy position of the Tinubu's government against the Niger's Junta. Nigeria has a rich record of external military deployments and operations for peace-keeping, enforcement and promotion of democracy across Africa. Although the government of Buhari (2015-2023), a Fulani from the North, supported ECOWAS mission and deployed the Nigerian military to enforce democratic transition in the Gambia in 2016, he approached the military coups in Mali (2020 and 2021) and Burkina Faso (January and September 2022) with silence. While this foreign policy decisions can be justified with Afrocentric and post-colonial non-interference principles and rational-choice around the national security interest, identity theory cannot ignored the significance of Fulani population in Mali (13.3%) and Burkina Faso (6.8%) and the possible implications on the government.³⁹

Conclusions

Domestic factors have been central, though not the only factors conditioning Nigeria's foreign policy positions. It is a well-known fact that Nigeria is characterized by diverse religious inclinations. This has negatively affected her citizens in their struggle with unity issues and in the country's relation with foreign nations.

³⁷ Colins, Chukwuka. Interview with Ponsah Saleh, Abuja, 11th March, 2026.

³⁸ AGUENE, IGNATIUS N. "THE ROLE OF DIASPORA IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE COUNTRY OF THE ORIGIN: THE NIGERIA EXAMPLE." *Caritas Journal of Management, Socia Sciences and Humanities* 4, no. 2 (2025): 1-15.

³⁹ Omede, Adedoyin J. "Nigeria's Relations with her Neighbours." *Studies of Tribes and Tribals* 4, no. 1 (2006): 7-17.

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In conclusion, the significance of ethno-regionalism and religion in Nigeria's foreign policy is extremely complicated, as it is entwined with political, environmental, and economic concerns. The twin plaques of ethnicity and religion have long tried to outplay each other in the struggle for control of key political positions and influencing policy decisions. These tussles have continuously shaped and unshaped Nigeria's domestic politics and foreign policy orientation. Generally, ethno-regional and religious forces have had both positive and negative effects on Nigeria's foreign policy. The products of these identity forces in Nigeria's foreign policy sometimes align with rational-choice and realism, while patrimonialism becomes too obvious in some cases. Accordingly, ethno-regional and religiously motivated actions are sometimes taken at the expense of the common good, as broadly conceived national interests are replaced with narrow and primordial considerations.

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